

FINANCIAL STATEMENT ANALYSIS AND DASHBOARD DEVELOPMENT USING FINANCIAL RATIOS

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Abstract. *A key instrument for assessing a company's financial performance and stability, financial accounting analysis forms the basis of strategic decision-making. The balance sheet, income statement, and cash flow statement are the three main financial statements that are thoroughly examined as part of this analytical process, which provides information about the entity's profitability, liquidity management, and overall financial health. By employing techniques such as financial ratio analysis, trend analysis, and industry benchmarking, analysts assess key financial aspects, including liquidity, solvency, operational efficiency, and profitability. A professional Business Performance Analysis is aimed to provide along with dashboard of past financial statements of one of the Pharmacy entities in Uzbekistan in 2022-2023, to visualizes the financial health and performance metrics of the company, particularly in managing costs and improving profitability in months where losses are indicated. Specifically, ratio calculation to identify the business performance and operational efficiency over the year, guiding decisions in management and investment targeted.*

Key words: *Management Accounting, dashboard, risk management, stakeholders, ratio calculations, financial ratios, profitability ratios, liquidity ratios, solvency ratios, efficiency ratio, Gross profit margin, Net profit margin, Current ratio, Quick ratio, Debt-to-equity ratio, Inventory turnover, Total asset turnover, Return on equity (ROE), Return on assets (ROA), The return days from trade receivables, The creditors turnover days ratio, Expense ratio, The return on trade receivable ratio, The return days from trade receivables.*

Introduction

Financial statement analysis plays a critical role in understanding a company's financial health, operational efficiency, and long-term sustainability. Financial ratios serve as core tools in this process, offering standardized measures to evaluate profitability, liquidity, solvency, and efficiency. With the rise of data-driven decision-making, dashboards have emerged as effective platforms for visually presenting key financial indicators, facilitating quick and strategic managerial responses. This study focuses on analyzing the financial statements of a pharmaceutical manufacturing company in Uzbekistan using key financial ratios and developing a financial dashboard based on the results.

Literature Review

Financial ratio analysis has long been recognized as a foundational method in evaluating financial performance. Brigham and Ehrhardt emphasize the classification of ratios into four main groups: liquidity, solvency, profitability, and efficiency. Profitability ratios, as discussed by Gitman and Zutter (2012), are crucial for assessing a company's ability to generate income from its resources. Ratios such as Gross Margin, ROA, and ROE allow comparisons against industry standards and historical performance.

Liquidity ratios, such as the Current Ratio and Quick Ratio, help determine the firm's short-term financial flexibility (Ross, Westerfield, & Jordan, 2010). Solvency ratios, including Debt-to-Equity and Interest Coverage, are essential for assessing long-term risk and capital structure (Brealey & Myers). Horngren et al. highlight the role of efficiency ratios in operational performance evaluation, especially in asset utilization.

Koller, Goedhart, and Wessels (2010) integrate financial ratios into broader valuation models and strategic financial management. Penman (2010) critiques the limitations of conventional ratio analysis, warning that accounting methods and market conditions can distort financial insights. These sources collectively form the conceptual framework for this study, guiding both the analytical approach and interpretation.

Analysis and Results

Methodology

This study employed both qualitative and quantitative methods to analyze financial data from a pharmaceutical company in Uzbekistan. The data was sourced from the company's internal financial reports and included income statements and balance sheets over a three-year period. Eleven financial ratios were calculated across four categories.

Key financial ratios to be acquainted with encompass:

Gross profit margin indicates the percentage of profit generated by the company after deducting direct cost of sales from revenue. The formula for calculating the gross profit margin is:

$$\text{Gross Profit Margin (\%)} = \left(\frac{\text{Revenue} - \text{Cost of Goods Sold}}{\text{Revenue}} \right) \times 100$$

Net profit margin reflects the percentage of profit generated by the company after deducting all expenses, including interest and tax, from revenue. The formula for calculating the net profit margin is:

$$\text{Net Profit Margin (\%)} = \left(\frac{\text{Net Profit}}{\text{Revenue}} \right) \times 100$$

Current ratio measures the company's ability to meet short-term liabilities within a year. The formula for the current ratio is:

$$\text{Current Ratio} = \frac{\text{Current Assets}}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$$

Quick ratio assesses the company's ability to settle short-term liabilities within a year using highly liquid assets exclusively. The formula for the quick ratio is:

$$\text{Quick Ratio} = \frac{\text{Current Assets} - \text{Inventory}}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$$

Debt-to-equity ratio indicates the proportion of debt to equity utilized by the company for financing. The formula for the debt-to-equity ratio is:

$$\text{Debt-to-Equity Ratio} = \frac{\text{Total Debt}}{\text{Total Equity}}$$

Inventory turnover measures how frequently the entire inventory is sold within a specific period. The formula for the inventory turnover is:

$$\text{Inventory Turnover} = \frac{\text{Cost of Goods Sold (COGS)}}{\text{Average Inventory}}$$

Total asset turnover assesses the efficiency with which the company generates revenue from its total assets. The formula for the total asset turnover is:

$$\text{Total Asset Turnover} = \frac{\text{Net Sales}}{\text{Average Total Assets}}$$

Dashboard description

Dashboard is a visual representation of data, designed to provide users with a quick and comprehensive view of key performance indicators (KPIs), metrics, and trends within an organization or system. They serve the purpose of facilitating data-driven decision-making by presenting information in a clear, concise, and easily understandable format.

Dashboard: Monitoring Business Performance of the entity in 2022-2023

The Dashboard displays a detailed financial performance of the company for the years 2022 and 2023, focusing on various critical financial metrics. Each panel is displayed within the dashboard to provide insights into different aspects of the company's financial health and operational efficiency.

To start with **Net Profit Margin**, a reduction from 10.31% in 2022 to 8.53% in 2023 indicates a decrease in profitability, which could result from increased costs or decreased revenue efficiency. Likewise, index of **Gross Profit Margin** saw a slight decrease from 22.98% in 2022 to 20.15% in 2023 suggesting that the cost of goods sold as a percentage of sales has increased, impacting the overall profitability. By contrast, **Total Expense Ratio** shows an increase from 8.5% in 2022 to 11.1% in 2023. This indicates bad control over expenses or a rise in operational costs relative to total revenue. Unlike this, trend of **Current Ratio** decreased dramatically from 6.0 in 2022 to 2.1 in 2023 where a significant drop suggests a reduction in the company's liquidity, potentially indicating tighter cash flow or higher short-term liabilities. Meanwhile, **Debt-to-Equity** increased sharply from 19.92% to 89.16% meaning a substantial increase in debt used to finance the company's assets relative to equity, indicating higher financial leverage and potential risk.

Like **Inventory Turnover** decreased from 8.0 in 2022 to 4.9 in 2023, the **Asset Turnover** also experienced a decline from 8.9 in 2022 to 4.9 in 2023. These falls suggest lower efficiency in managing inventory and assets to generate sales.

A lower **ROP** suggests that the company is using less credit from suppliers or perhaps improving its cash position to negotiate better terms, which could be favorable in maintaining good supplier relationships but might also indicate less efficient use of financial leverage. However, a stability in ROR is beneficial, as it indicates that the company does not face increased difficulty in collecting from its customers, which is crucial for maintaining cash flow. Understanding these specific functions within the broader financial context is to better analyze the company's operational efficiency and financial strategy, particularly in managing its working capital components—payables and receivables—which are crucial for short-term financial health.

Return on Assets (ROA) saw a downward trend from 51.61% in 2022 to 42.05% in 2023, parallely **Return on Equity (ROE)** dropped from 79.54% in 2022 to 42.05% in 2023. Both reductions reflect declining effectiveness in utilizing the company's assets and equity to produce profits.

Discussion

In the Dashboard a series of challenges faced by the company from 2022 to 2023 illustrated, that is marked by reduced efficiency in asset and inventory management, increased financial leverage, and decreased profitability and liquidity. The changes in these key financial indicators signal a need for strategic adjustments in operations, financial management, and perhaps cost control measures to improve financial health and reduce vulnerability due to high debt levels. By this information, Stakeholders, who need to consider these insights critical for making informed decisions regarding future investments, operational strategies, and financial management practices.

Conclusion

The company underwent several challenges and areas of concern that necessitate immediate attention and strategic adjustments. Operational efficiencies also appear to have weakened, as evidenced by decreased inventory and asset turnover rates, which could impact the company's cash flow and operational agility. The current ratio's sharp decline highlights potential liquidity issues, pointing towards a need for better cash management practices to ensure that the company can meet its short-term obligations. While there are indications of improved expense management, the overall financial health of the company is precarious unfortunately. To navigate these challenges, it is critical for the company to implement rigorous financial controls, reassess its operational strategies, and possibly diversify its revenue streams to stabilize its financial position and foster sustainable growth. Immediate action in these areas will be crucial to reversing the negative trends and setting a foundation for future stability and profitability.

Recommendations

Based on the comprehensive financial performance dashboards provided for the entity from 2022 to 2023, several recommendations suggested to enhance the company's financial health and operational efficiency. For instance, by Optimization on Cost Management. Notably high cost of sales relative to revenue suggests a need to streamline production processes or negotiate better terms with suppliers to enhance gross margins. Also, analyzing administrative expenses, particularly those showing significant variance through the months, and identifying areas for cost reduction without compromising operational integrity is a real concern. In addition, the company should stabilize Revenue Fluctuations by exploring strategies to stabilize revenue fluctuations seen throughout the year. This might involve diversifying product lines, enhancing marketing efforts, or entering new markets. Despite a decrease in overall revenue, efforts should be made to improve net and gross profit margins through cost optimization and pricing

strategies. The significant increase in debt-to-equity ratio is another urgent concern. The company should consider strategies to either reduce debt levels or enhance equity through retained earnings or equity financing to ensure financial stability and reduce interest cost burden. A proactive approach to managing liquidity should be adopted given the sharp decline in the current ratio. This includes better management of working capital, improving cash flows through quicker receivable turnovers, and better inventory management. Given the constant tax rate impact, there is a room for improved tax planning strategies to ensure that the company maximizes its after-tax profitability. Close monitoring of financial operations such as finance costs and net foreign exchange gains or losses is crucial. The owner of the entity is suggested to consider leveraging financial hedging strategies to mitigate risks due to currency fluctuations. Likewise, there is a need to improve asset and inventory management to boost turnover rates, which helps in freeing up cash locked in slow-moving inventory and underutilized assets, thoroughly thought strategic review of the business plan and growth strategy is essential there. This should include an analysis of the market, competitive positioning, and innovation potential to regain growth momentum. By implementing these recommendations, the entity can hope to address its current financial challenges, optimize operational performance, and set a robust foundation for sustainable growth and profitability in the coming years. Identifying the negative correlation of Gross profit and Net income is equally essential.

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